

SolDAC: Full Spectrum Solar-Powered Direct CO₂ Capture from Air and Conversion in Ethylene

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Abstract

CO₂-derived chemicals are expensive and only few will be able to meet the current market expectations, settled in decades of fossil fuel economy. Ethylene can be one of the few chemicals that can be produced from a 100% renewable route to the condition that specific targets are achieved. The SolDAC project endeavours in all scientific challenges preventing the demonstration of a sustainable route for renewable Ethylene. A process is proposed that captures CO₂ from the air and convert it to Ethylene in an electrochemical unit. The process is powered by a highly efficient solar energy technology that collects the full spectrum of solar radiation.

Keywords: Full Spectrum Solar Energy, Direct Air Capture, Photo-electrochemical conversion, carbon dioxide.

Introduction

Reducing carbon emissions also requires finding alternative pathways for producing organic chemical compounds derived from fossil fuels. Ethylene is an essential chemical intermediary for plastics, with an annual global production rate of 185 Mt [1]. Traditionally, its production is by steam cracking of crude oil in a high energy-demanding process, resulting in a global carbon footprint of 0.2 Gt [1] emitted annually. Renewable Ethylene can be obtained by electrochemical reduction of atmospheric CO₂ using electricity from renewable sources that is a promising production route to close the carbon loop and mitigate CO₂ emissions [2]. However, the technological viability of this process relies on the efficiency of the renewable source, on the

purification of extremely dilute CO₂ and on affordable electrochemical catalysts that overcome critical factors such as poor activity, selectivity, and energy efficiency [3]. The Full Spectrum Solar Direct Air Capture and Conversion project (SolDAC) gathers eight research institutions and companies from four countries (UK: The University of Edinburgh and University of St Andrews; Spain: IREC, University of Lleida, LOMARTOV SL, Comet; Italy: CNR-ITAE; Belgium: EIM) and aims at demonstrating the sustainable production of renewable Ethylene from atmospheric CO₂ and water through an innovative process.

Overall process

The process is organised into three sections: a Full Spectrum Solar collector (FSS), a Direct Air Capture unit (DAC), and a Photo-Electrochemical Conversion stack (PEC). The main energy and mass fluxes and the interrelations among units are depicted in Fig 1.

Fig. 1 - The SolDAC process for conversion of atmospheric CO₂ into Ethylene.

Full Spectrum Solar Collector (FSS)

A solar energy collection system able to capture the full spectrum of solar energy powers both DAC and PEC. The power from the FSS comes to the downstream processes in three forms: electrical, thermal, and optical. Ultraviolet light and infra-red are absorbed and transported in form of thermal energy. The visible spectrum wavelengths are collected and converted in electrical power and voltage saving. The overall process efficiency depends on the efficiency of the acceptance angle and the optical efficiency of the Fresnel Concentrator [4]. However, the efficiency needs to be evaluated from the receiver to the thermal and photo-voltaic (electric). Regarding the thermal efficiency, it is strongly dependent on the temperature of the carrier [5]. A higher thermal efficiency is observed in lower temperatures, due to the reduction of heat losses by convection to the ambient. The photo-voltaic (PV) efficiency is related to the photo-carrier, like an optical fiber, and to the photo-voltaic cell, that converts light into electricity. The goal of FSS in terms of electrical efficiency is to convert the 22% of the incident power by

selecting the most efficient photons based on the PV spectral response. On the other hand, the foreseen thermal efficiency to be achieved by the hybrid receiver is expected to reach 38%, which means a target global efficiency of 60%. This figure goes beyond the state-of-the-art by increasing the efficiency of the reference system by 10% [4].

Direct Air Capture Unit (DAC)

A DAC unit consisting of a combination of capture and concentration adsorption beds [6] embedding different nanoporous materials is able to capture ultra-dilute CO₂ (410 ppm) from ambient air and concentrate it before it is used in the PEC to produce ethylene. Usually, nanoporous materials with good CO₂ affinity also present affinity for water. Due to that, a material with good CO₂ capacity and step isotherm for water (H₂O) is preferable in the process. To ensure a low water adsorption, a water harvesting step is considered to reduce relative humidity before the capture bed. A fraction of the water removed from air can be used in electrochemical conversion. The energy consumption in the DAC unit primarily comes from the temperature swings. Therefore, using low-temperature-heat (below the current state-of-the-art 80 °C [7]) to regenerate the sorbent is preferable to make the process more economically attractive [8]. The project targets a regeneration at 60 °C, reducing the primary energy consumption to purify and compress CO₂ from 8.51 MJ/kg_{CO2} (adapted from [9]) to 3 MJ/ kg_{CO2}.

Photo-Electrochemical Conversion stack (PEC)

Previous studies have demonstrated that Cu is the only pure metal that can produce C₂+ products with substantial selectivity [10]. For this reason, there have been several investigations on tuning the composition and morphology of Cu catalysts to optimise the conversion of CO₂ [11]. The PEC unit uses an energy flow (in the form of photons and/or electricity) in a copper-based catalyst to convert CO₂ to Ethylene. Cu-based catalysts (e.g. Ag, Bi, Sn) were prepared through optimised electrodeposition and wet-chemistry methods. The catalysts were deposited onto carbon paper (Gas Diffusion Layer) and were used as gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs). The use of GDEs has demonstrated the capacity to obtain high current densities (>200 mA cm⁻²) by supporting the catalyst on a microporous substrate at a gas-liquid interface [12]. For characterising the electrochemical performance of the catalysts, a flow electrolyser has been used to reduce the captured CO₂ into the targeted renewable chemicals such as Ethylene with targeted faradaic efficiencies > 70%. Liquid products such as ethanol are also expected as by-products, giving a combined C₂+ efficiency > 85%. Moreover, the PEC unit foresees the integration of photoelectrodes in the anode side, able to provide additional photovoltage under illumination, in order to decrease the overall energy requirement and to directly utilise photons from the FSS unit.

Process Thermodynamics

Likewise, many other renewable energy-powered chemicals from CO₂, Ethylene can result unbearably expensive, with no real market acceptance. Furthermore, the life-cycle emissions for the construction of the sub-processes have to at least be compensated by the emissions avoided and by those stored underground (geological storage is one of the options present in in Fig. 1). The mass and energy balances of each one of the sub-processes and of the overall SoLDAC process can help to identify if the SoLDAC project has chances to be sustainable.

Aiming to achieve a defined production rate of ethylene, the process mass balance starts from the PEC stack. A simplified mass balance was implemented based on the Faradaic efficiencies

for ethanol, ethylene and hydrogen, the electrode area and the current density used. An excess factor for the CO₂ demand was introduced to ensure a reaction tending to ethylene and not the by-product (ethanol or hydrogen). The electrical energy required for reaction was calculated based on the specific energy to convert CO₂ to ethylene and the overall process efficiency.

For the DAC unit, a mass balance was used to relate CO₂ purity, recovery, and flowrate at the end of the separation with the air composition and feed flowrate. Air composition was simplified in H₂O, CO₂ and N₂. All other gases present in air were lumped in N₂ concentration. An excess factor for CO₂ was used in the Direct Air Capture, and the CO₂ that surpasses the PEC demand was used for geological storage and consider in the economic analysis as carbon credits. The DAC unit is powered by electrical and thermal energy simultaneously. Electrical energy is used to power fans to move air through the system. The total electricity demand was calculated from the fan efficiency, pressure drop across the system, and the processed volumetric flowrate. Thermal energy is used to regenerate the beds and recover CO₂ that was adsorbed. The heat power was obtained from the minimum work of separation and the efficiency of this process.

The FSS area was calculated to supply the energetic requirements determined in the previous units. As discussed, the full spectrum solar is able to generate electrical, thermal, and photovoltaic power. The total electrical power needs to adequate the PEC and the DAC process requirements, while the thermal power complies with only the DAC unit. Solar energy (photons) is directly used in the anode side of the electrochemical stack with adapted photovoltaics to decrease cell potential and reduce electric energy demand. An energy balance for the FSS was developed to relate the energy generation with the Fresnel area. The calculations considered the conversion efficiency of light to electricity and to heat, the overall efficiency of the Fresnel, and the mean beam irradiance, to relate the energy generation with the Fresnel area.

From the mass and energy balances described, a small plant with capacity to produce 1 kg/day of ethylene needs to process 34 ton/day of air, capturing about 17kg/day of CO₂. To power that pilot-plant, an area of 32 m² is required for the full spectrum solar. In this configuration, 9% of the CO₂ that was captured is used for geological storage.

In addition to the balances done, an economical and environmental check was performed to evaluate the feasibility of the proposal. Fig. 2 depicts the results from those studies. For the environmental analysis, the carbon footprint values of each unit were set at: 0.32 kg of CO₂ emitted per kg of CO₂ removed for the DAC unit, 3.05 kg of CO₂ emitted per m² of the PEC unit, and 0.025 kg of CO₂ emitted per kWhel generated in the FSS unit. These were based on the Life Cycle Assessments of similar technologies, published in other works [13, 14, 15]. For the economic analysis, chemical prices were assumed at their current market value. The costs of the technologies were estimated from published data to observe the price cost to accomplish a carbon-neutral process that is economically viable.

Fig. 2 – Results from the pilot plant to produce 1 kg/day of ethylene and 0.2 kg/day of by-product ethanol.

If the objectives of the project are met, a total life cycle emission of 0.66 ton of CO₂, sourced mainly by DAC emissions (99.4%). However, the CO₂ removed from atmosphere by the process is counterbalanced in less than 6 months of operation. After 20 years of lifetime, the CO₂ removed is more than 62 times greater than the amount emitted in a life cycle.

The highest costs involved in the process are related with the full spectrum solar, representing 79% of the plant total cost. For the current technology price [16], FSS costs surpass the total revenues, showing a necessity to reduce this price in half for a feasible process. This reduction can be achieved by buying down the technology specific cost or by reducing the area requirement of the FSS. In which, the area is a consequence of the individual process efficiencies and the energy conversion in the FSS. Therefore, by tuning the energy efficiency of the process, the calculations showed that the pilot-plant can be economically balanced while having a great carbon-negative potential.

Conclusions

The SoldAC project has an ambitious objective to prove a carbon neutral production of Ethylene by removing CO₂ from air. The preliminary results obtained from the mass and energy balance shows the possibility to go beyond carbon neutrality and achieve a carbon-negative process, with 9 % of the CO₂ captured being used for geological storage. Coupling a Direct Air Capture unit to the Photo-Electrical Chemical stack is a mandatory measure to produce ethylene from a non-fossil-fuel-derivative that is also zero-carbon emission. Finally, by using power obtained from an independent and renewable energy source, the project benefits from not adding pressure on the energy system while relying in a replicable setting of energy production (solar energy). Overall, the project shows promising results to be a pioneer in producing Ethylene with 100% renewable route, that is energetically sufficient and modular carbon neutral, and it is replicable in a wide range of locations. The SoldAC project aims to reinvent the Ethylene industry by replacing the current carbon-positive routes.

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